

Deliverable D3.2

Title: First report on SECRETed Molecular Networks: Publicly available molecular structures and inference of associated features to molecular fingerprints

Lead Beneficiary

IDE R&D

Delivery Date

31st May 2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000794. This publication reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Deliverable No.	D3.2
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package	3
Task	3.1
Lead Beneficiary	IDENER R&D
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	UoA
Reviewers	IDENER team
Due date of deliverable	31 st May 2022
Actual submission date	31 st May 2022
Main Author/Contributors	IDENER team

Project Acronym	SECRETed
Project Title	Sustainable Exploitation of bio-based Compounds Revealed and Engineered from naTural sources
Activity	RIA Research and Innovation action
Call	H2020-FNR-2020-2
Funding Scheme	Grant Agreement No: 101000794

Document History				
Version	Date	Beneficiary	Author/Reviwer	Notes
1.0	05-20-2022	IDE R&D	IDENER team	First draft
2.0	05-30-2022	IDE R&D	IDENER team	Corrections applied.

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Executive Summary

The SECRETed project will fully exploit the potential of Systems and Synthetic Biology toolboxes and their application within aquatic biotechnology to develop novel hybrid compounds for the agrochemical, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and chemistry sectors. Biosynthetic pathways of marine and extremophilic microorganisms will be reverse engineered to infer the individual roles of their constituent genes, which will be further combined for the production of non-natural biosurfactants and siderophores with tailor-made properties.

Biosurfactants are compounds with a surface-active nature tendency to adsorb at interfaces, while siderophores have the ability to chelate and transport Fe^{3+} ions. The amphiphilic nature of biosurfactants and marine siderophores provides an exciting opportunity to develop methods of biosynthesis that would enable the exchange of their hydrophobic and hydrophilic parts, among other structural changes. The development of hybrid molecules would allow the exploration of new-to-nature compounds endowed with the combination of their respective properties, to address new applications.

Machine Learning algorithms, the inspection of databases, and new experimental and computational-based data will be employed to build a unique microbial amphiphilic compound chemical space to identify the desired genetic mechanisms. Detected genes will be reverse engineered to standardise and modularize associated metabolic elements, with the purpose of broadening their benefits by searching for Industrial-driven formulations based on suitable microbial hosts. The Design-Build-Test-Learn methodological steps will be used to produce new microbial strains that support the selected genetic elements and satisfy sustainable industrial processes.

Deliverable D3.2 is a public report produced in the context of WP3: “Databases integration and Industry-driven designs”. In Task 3.1: “Machine learning approaches to survey databases for siderophore and biosurfactants information”, ML algorithms have been deployed and applied to survey databases and scientific publications. Specifically, subtask 3.1.1: “Molecular Families inspection” focuses on collecting information about structures of compounds, linked properties, and biological activities of biosurfactants and amphiphilic siderophores contained in publicly available databases and available information in scientific literature.

Together with subtask 3.1.2: “Amphiphilic siderophores and biosurfactant biosynthetic gene cluster analysis” the aim of Task 3.1 is to construct a unique microbial amphiphilic compound space comprehending molecular structures, physicochemical characteristics, associated bioactivities, and revealed genetic mechanisms responsible for their biosynthesis.

The present report summarises obtained molecular data, informs about how SECRETed compounds have been clustered in Molecular Families, and describes QSAR modelling efforts and their involvement in structure-property-driven retrosynthesis algorithm.

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1. Introduction

Chemical diversity and complexity are examples of properties to guide the design and selection of new small molecules. These properties may have significant implications in many areas of research, including but not limited to drug and probe discovery. Systematic exploration of the chemical diversity and complexity of small molecules can be carried out using different strategies. Among them, molecular networking (MN) has proved to be a very efficient tool for rapidly identify new Natural Products (NPs) within complex mixtures^{1,2}. MN also helps to explore the chemical space of potential chemical analogues based on fragmentation data and other integrated features like bioactivity¹. Chemical space refers to a multidimensional conceptual space in which dimensions represent properties of molecules calculated from the molecular structure and grouped in a feature vector, or fingerprint³. In such chemical spaces, each molecule is placed at the coordinates corresponding to its properties, and the distance between two molecules measures their similarity. Since the physicochemical and biological properties of molecules are determined by their molecular structures, one can use the distribution of molecules in chemical space to guide a search for a particular property³. Molecular Families (MFs) would be then the group of nearest neighbours with the most similar properties to the reference molecule and a clear structural signature⁴.

Individual studies have characterised a multitude of biosurfactants and siderophores, providing their structure and some functional features^{5,6}. Still, all this information is hidden in unstructured text formats, and these parameters need to be collected and clustered into a comprehensive meta-analysis.

Central to SECRETed main objectives is to construct a unique microbial amphiphilic compound space comprehending molecular structures, physicochemical characteristics, associated bioactivities, and revealed genetic mechanisms responsible for their biosynthesis.

SECRETed biochemical space will then be utilised to model the structure-property relationship underlying previous observations. SECRETed will exploit these structure-property relationship models to identify the major structural elements in charge of desired properties.

Then, SECRETed biochemical space determination and structure-property-driven retrosynthesis algorithms will inform SECRETed end-users about the possible interesting blends and their suitability to satisfy their wide use in different industrial sectors.

This report establishes the advancements regarding data collection and conciliation; its organisation in Molecular Families based on molecular fingerprints and clustering algorithms; the distribution of SECRETed key data along with the different clusters; and the modular comprehensive understanding of biosurfactants and siderophores, which eases further steps of SECRETed project.

¹ Ramos et al., *Nat Prod Rep.* 36(7):960-980. (2019).

² Arora and Banerjee. *Curr Top Med Chem.* 19(2):101-102 (2019).

³ Awale et al. *Chimia (Aarau).* 71(10):661-666(2017).

⁴ Nguyen et al., *PNAS.* 110(28):E2611-E2620 (2011).

⁵ Liu et al., *Int J Mol Sci.* 16(3): 4814–4837 (2015).

⁶ Paulino et al., *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 100(24):10265-10293 (2016).

2. SECRETed Biochemical space construction.

2.1. Databases inspection and data collection.

Currently, reliance on a disparate set of non-standardized, insular, and specialised databases presents a series of challenges for data access, both within the discipline and for integration and interoperability between related fields.

To obtain and refine SECRETed molecular information, the name, the Pubchem ID (when present), and the organism or origin from molecules described as siderophores or as biosurfactants were collected by searching “biosurfactant” or “siderophore” respectively in PubMed database⁷ and by manual searching in search engines⁸.

This initial list was completed by searching in SurfDB database⁹ for biosurfactants and the Siderophore Base, the Web Data Base of Microbial Siderophores¹⁰ for siderophores. Natural product Atlas (NPA) database¹¹ files were downloaded and filtered by searching for “biosurfactant” and “siderophore” to expand the initial collection. Furthermore, the molecules collected otherwise were also explored in NPA to obtain additional information about the natural origin of the compounds.

PubChem ID was used to web scrap for most chemically-well-defined biosurfactants and siderophores by searching by Name, SMILES, inchi, and chemical structure.

The name of the molecules and/or the different identifiers, mainly Inchi, SMILES, and Pubchem IDs, were used to search for experimental data in several ways:

- COLLEction of Open Natural ProdUCts (COCONUT)¹² database was fully downloaded and managed by MongoDB. Properties of previously collected molecules were retrieved by PubChem ID or by SMILES.
- The LOTUS¹³ initiative was also explored to obtain structure-organism pairs that establish relationships between distinct molecular structures and the living organisms from which they were identified (More details in Deliverable D3.3).
- Inchi identifiers and SMILES from our molecules were used to filter the available information from the Natural Product Activity and Species Source Database (NPASS¹⁴), which provided information on species sources and biological activities of natural products.
- Files that encompass Standardized experimental data, as well as structural properties and identifiers from molecules, were downloaded from the Comprehensive Marine Natural Products Database (CMNPD)¹⁵. Inchi identifiers and SMILES from our molecules were used to filter the available information about experimental assays.

⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁸ <https://www.google.com>

⁹ <https://www.biosurfdb.org>

¹⁰ http://bertrandsamuel.free.fr/siderophore_base/siderophores.php

¹¹ <https://www.npatlas.org>

¹² <https://coconut.naturalproducts.net/>

¹³ <https://lotus.naturalproducts.net/>

¹⁴ <http://bidd.group/NPASS/>

¹⁵ <https://www.cmnpd.org/>

- PubChem database was interrogated to retrieve functional assays of the collected molecules.
- Pubmed database and search engines were used to manually complete functional information from the literature, by combining the searchings:
 - "Biosurfactant", in combination with critical micelle concentration (CMC), emulsification index (EI24), surface tension, Antifungal, Antimicrobial act, Antitumoral, Bioremediation, Antiviral, Antimalarial.
 - "Siderophore" combined with metals, Pb, Al, Fe, Cu, CAS test, ChromeAzuro, metal affinity, Antifungal, Antimicrobial act, Antitumoral, Bioremediation Antiviral, Antimalarial.

Finally, those compounds with defined biosynthetic pathways and related Biosynthetic Gene Clusters (BGCs) were identified and highlighted (See deliverable D3.3) to serve as “anchoring points” for the retrosynthesis algorithms (Figure 1, Table 1).

Since, in some cases, structural depictions were inferred from literature, and they are not present in any other database, collected data was associated with unique SECRETed identifiers. Thus, we could collect 2139 unique compounds, 1606 biosurfactants, and 572 siderophores.

Included in said 1606 Biosurfactants, 1235 had structural depictions and PubChem compound id which facilitated the extraction of further information (molecular structures and molecular fingerprints). On the other hand, of 572 compounds defined as Siderophores, 492 had structural depictions and PubChem compound id.

Overall, we could obtain more than 1700 molecular structures by cross-referencing other NP-related databases containing their unique data coverage (Figure 1, Table 1).

Figure 1 Euler diagram showing the SECRETed NPs database consolidation efforts (detailed information in Table 1).

Table 1: SECRETed molecular data origin from NPs consolidation efforts

Data origin	Counting
Biosynthetic pathway info	7
Biosynthetic pathway info Coconut LOTUS NPA PubChem	14
Biosynthetic pathway info Coconut LOTUS PubChem	2
Biosynthetic pathway info Coconut PubChem	1
Biosynthetic pathway info LOTUS NPA NPASS PubChem	6
Biosynthetic pathway info LOTUS NPA PubChem	101
Biosynthetic pathway info LOTUS PubChem	8
Biosynthetic pathway info NPA PubChem	3
Biosynthetic pathway info NPASS PubChem	1
Biosynthetic pathway info PubChem	11
Coconut LOTUS	1
Coconut LOTUS NPA NPASS PubChem	18
Coconut LOTUS NPA PubChem	145
Coconut LOTUS NPASS PubChem	8
Coconut LOTUS PubChem	11
Coconut NPA PubChem	6
Coconut PubChem	40
LOTUS NPA	1
LOTUS NPA NPASS PubChem	40
LOTUS NPA PubChem	638
LOTUS NPASS PubChem	14
LOTUS PubChem	44
NPA	1
NPA PubChem	53
NPASS PubChem	5
Pubchem	548

2.2. Summary of SECRETed collected data.

As explained in the previous section, included in said 1606 Biosurfactants, 1235 had a PubChem compound id which facilitated the extraction of further information (molecular structures and molecular fingerprints).

In some cases, the tag “Biosurfactant” also extracted information from chemical modifications of natural compounds, herein referred to as “Natural-derived” (more than 400 compounds, Figure 2A). That information was kept in order to feed Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) models and retrosynthesis algorithms.

Regarding the main values that characterise Biosurfactants, after eliminating those that did not include a molecular structure, we could obtain 298 compounds with CMC values, 126 with Kraft temperature (also known as Kraft point), and 21 with Surface tension coefficients (Figure 2B).

Overall, 8266 PubChem functional assays were recovered from only 171 biosurfactants. Most of them contained information related to antibacterial, antimicrobial activities, and antitumoral assays (Figure 1C).

Figure 2. Summary of Biosurfactant collected data. A) Chemical nature. B) Number of compounds with associated Biosurfactant values. C) Number of bioassays associated with Biosurfactants.

On the other hand, of 572 compounds defined as Siderophores, 494 had a PubChem compound id which facilitated the extraction of further information (molecular structures and molecular fingerprints).

In a similar way to biosurfactants, the tag “Siderophore” also extracted information from chemical modifications of natural compounds, herein referred to as “Natural-derived”. In this case, only 21 compounds were kept in order to feed Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) models and retrosynthesis algorithms (Figure 3A).

Regarding the main values that characterise Siderophores, we inspected databases for ChromoAzurool tests and affinity for other metals. This time we could only obtain 52 compounds showing the ChromoAzurool tests and 19 compounds indicating an affinity to metals other than iron (Figure 3B).

Finally, 1825 PubChem functional assays were recovered from only 52 Siderophores. Most of them are related to antitumoral, Gene expression modulation, and antibacterial assays (Figure 3C).

Figure 4 shows the 171 biosurfactants and 52 siderophores and their number of biological assays when clustering their molecular structures into MFs (see section 3).

Figure 3. Summary of Siderophores collected data. A) Chemical nature. B) Number of compounds with associated Siderophore values. C) Number of bioassays associated with Siderophores.

Figure 4. Distribution of A) antimicrobial activity assays and B) antitumoral activity along SECRETed MFs.

3. Molecular diversity and complexity of SECRETed chemical space

The diversity and complexity of molecules in a chemical library can be evaluated in multiple ways, mainly depending on the data under scrutiny and the goals of the study.

The most common ways to represent molecules in chemoinformatic applications are molecular descriptors (including physicochemical properties and molecular fingerprints) and chemical scaffolds¹⁶.

Molecular descriptors frequently used to describe chemical libraries include molecular weight (MW), number of rotatable bonds (RBs), hydrogen bond acceptors (HBAs), hydrogen bond donors (HBDs), topological polar surface area (TPSA), and the octanol/water partition coefficient (SlogP), which are properties commonly used as descriptors to represent lead-like, drug-like, or medicinally relevant chemical spaces.

Although informative and intuitive to interpret, physicochemical descriptors do not capture several structural features contained in the molecules. For instance, it is not uncommon that two compounds with very different chemical structures can have comparable MW and other drug-like properties. That is why in SECRETed, calculated Molecular descriptors were employed to perform Quantitative Structure-Activity(Property) Relationship (QSA(P)R) models (see section 4).

In its place, molecular fingerprints are especially useful for similarity calculations, such as database searching or clustering, generally measuring similarity as the Tanimoto coefficient¹⁷.

3.1. SECRETed Molecular Families clustering.

In order to cluster SECRETed compounds in MFs, the distance or similarity between the different chemical structures contained in the dataset needs to be measured.

Classical fingerprints, such as Morgan's¹⁸, have reported a good performance when being used as features in the development of a property predictive models. Specially when they perceive the presence of specific circular substructures around each atom in a molecule, which is predictive of the biological activities of small organic molecules¹⁹. However, they may have a poor perception of the global features of molecules such as size and shape. Nevertheless, the concept of similarity between chemical structures is ambiguous depending on the application. To surpass this problem, MAP4 fingerprint²⁰ was expected to be able to be employed in a larger variety of tasks as well as in dealing with no matter which type of chemical structure. As explained by the authors: "Such a fingerprint would provide an elegant, unified description of molecules across very different sizes and might also be useful to describe molecules of an intermediate size such as large natural products and metabolites."

¹⁶ Sing et al., *J. Chem. Inf. Model.*, 49 (2009)

¹⁷ Nikolova and Jaworska. *QSAR Comb. Sci.*, 22 (2003)

¹⁸ Rogers D, Hahn M. *J Chem Inf Model* 50:742–754. (2010)

¹⁹ Riniker S, Landrum GA. *J Cheminform* 5:26.(2013)

²⁰ Capecchi et al. *J Cheminform* 12:43 (2020)

The suitability of MAP4 fingerprint comes from the fact that it combines the benefits of two complementary approaches: ECFP and Atom-pair. While the first performs well when describing the properties of small molecules, the second can capture the structural features of large molecules.

The selected algorithm to perform the clustering task was Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering. The reason was twofold:

- The clustering can be trained to employ the distance matrix instead of examples' features if other than 'ward' linkage is employed. This fact helps save computation time and when dealing with molecular structure descriptions that cannot be represented in the Euclidean space (for instance, MAP4).
- A dendrogram can be easily built for visualisation purposes from the concatenation of different clustering models by varying the number of clusters or the threshold distance.

The linkage of the algorithm was chosen as complete, attempting to ensure that the maximum common substructure²¹ (MCS) of a cluster is kept as representative as possible. The number of clusters was obtained by using an *in house* modified silhouette coefficient analysis that considers the intra-cluster MCS average similarity. In this way, by favouring the formation of clusters with consistent common molecular scaffolds, the implementation of retrosynthesis algorithms is facilitated.

The modified silhouette coefficient was scaled to be in the range [0,1] and it is represented in the figure below for every possible value of the number of clusters (from 2 to N-1).

Figure 5. Modified Silhouette coefficient analysis.

²¹ Conte et al. Inter. J. Pattern Recognit. Artif. Intell.18:265–298. (2004).

Figure 5 shows that there exist an optimum range of number of clusters that maximizes the modified Silhouette Coefficient. The point at which the tendency of the Silhouette Coefficient starts to decrease is at 767 clusters. Interestingly, siderophores and biosurfactants MFs were majoritarily independent (Figure 6A).

In other words, the defined distance cut-off by the silhouette analysis was 0.597. Any pair of compounds whose molecular distance was higher were not connected (Figure 6A). This led to the formation of 540 unconnected compounds (372 for biosurfactants and 168 for siderophores), 139 clusters of 2 compounds (86 for biosurfactants and 53 for siderophores), 63 clusters of 3 compounds (39 for biosurfactants and 24 for siderophores), continuing in this way in a negative exponential decay till obtaining single clusters with more than 14 compounds (Figure 6B).

Figure 6. A) SECRETed biosurfactants and siderophores clustered in MFs B) Number of clusters by number of compounds defined in SECRETed MFs (circles) and number of clusters by number of compounds containing at least one member with defined biosynthetic gene cluster and biosynthetic pathway (triangles).

Of those, clusters with at least one compound containing refined biosynthetic pathway information are highlighted (Figure 6B, triangles). Said clusters contain essential “anchoring points” that serve to pave the way for retrosynthesis efforts (See section 5 and deliverable D3.3).

3.2. SECRETed Molecular descriptors and Biosurfactants R-group decomposition.

A molecular descriptor is defined as the “final result of a logical and mathematical procedure, which transforms chemical information encoded within a symbolic representation of a molecule into a useful number or the result of some standardised experiment”²².

QSA(P)R models (see section 4) frequently use molecular descriptors. They are studied to predict the activity, toxicity, and other properties resulting from the chemical structures of compounds.

To determine the chemo-mathematical pattern defining each biosurfactant in the database, a total of 1613 2D descriptors were calculated, using the Mordred²³ software. Molecular descriptors frequently used to describe chemical libraries include molecular weight (MW, Figure 7), number of rotatable bonds (RBs), hydrogen bond acceptors (HBAs), hydrogen bond donors (HBDs), topological polar surface area (TPSA), and the octanol/water partition coefficient (SlogP), which are properties commonly used as descriptors to represent lead-like, drug-like, or medicinally relevant chemical spaces²⁴. After performing variable reduction of the descriptors, those showing constant values and those with at least one missing value were discarded. Finally, 800 descriptors were selected to be used in the modelling strategy.

Figure 7. SECRETed Biosurfactant MFs Molecular Weight (g/mol).

To obtain strong and reliable QSA(P)R models, the database was grouped into different chemical families, based on the presence of certain functional groups (Table 2).

²² Todeschini R, Consonni V. Molecular descriptors for chemoinformatics. Wiley-VCH, Weinheim(2009)

²³ Moriwaki et al., J Cheminform. Feb 6;10(1):4.(2018)

²⁴ Lipinski Drug Discov. Today Technol., 1 pp. 337-341 (2004),

It is worth highlighting that biosurfactant R-group decomposition was mostly consistent with SECRETed clustering efforts, as it is shown by the overall homogeneity of SECRETed clusters (Figure 8).

Table 2: Biosurfactant database classified by R-group.

Code	Chemical family	Chemical formula	Number of BS compounds
1	Acid	(R-COOH)	378
2	Alcohol	(R-OH)	90
3	Ketone	(R-CO-R)	256
4	Amide	(R-CO-NR ₂)	217
5	Ester	(R-COO-R)	109
6	Quaternary ammonium salt	(N ⁺ -R ₄)	45
7	Phosphate	(PO ₄ ³⁻) and (R-O-PO-(OR) ₂)	34
8	Sulfate and Sulfonate	(SO ₄ ²⁻), (SO ₂ -(OR) ₂) and (R-SO ₃ ³⁻)	127
9	Acetate, carbamate carboxylate	(CH ₃ -COO-R), (NR ₂ -COO-R) and (R-COO-)	39

Code	Chemical family	Chemical formula
1	Acid	(R-COOH)
2	Alcohol	(R-OH)
3	Ketone	(R-CO-R)
4	Amide	(R-CO-NR ₂)
5	Ester	(R-COO-R)
6	Quaternary ammonium salt	(N ⁺ -R ₄)
7	Phosphate	(PO ₄ ³⁻) (R-O-PO-(OR) ₂)
8	Sulfate and Sulfonate	(SO ₄ ²⁻) (SO ₂ -(OR) ₂) y (R-SO ₃ ³⁻)
9	Acetate, carbamate and Carboxylate	(CH ₃ -COO-R), (NR ₂ -COO-R) y (R-COO ⁻)

Figure 8. SECRETed Biosurfactant MFs R-group decomposition.

4. SECRETed Biosurfactants first QSA(P)R approaches to model key parameters

4.1. Surfactant key parameters.

In the processes for study, development and application of surfactants, a broad range of data concerning their properties and activities have been accumulated. For example, the balance between hydrophobic and hydrophilic parts, hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB), is responsible for special properties of these amphiphilic compounds in solutions such as adsorption on the surfaces and interfaces and formation of self-assembly aggregates. Based on the HLB values, a biosurfactant will be an emulsifier, antifoaming agent and wetting agent which are desirable properties in cosmetic products, among other fields. In addition to that, Elongating the hydrocarbon chain makes the molecule more hydrophobic. The greater the hydrophobicity of the surfactant, the greater tendency to form micelles²⁵. Other important parameters are critical micelle concentration (CMC), and Krafft temperature (TK), which provides essential information about the activity and stability of microemulsions (Figure 9²⁶).

Figure 9. A) Schematical representation of the solubility curve for surfactants B) Plot of surface tension versus log of the bulk phase concentration for an aqueous solution of a surfactant.

The Krafft temperature (TK, also known as Krafft point) is the temperature at which surfactant solubility equals the CMC (that is the concentration at which surfactant monomers start to aggregate into micelles). Above TK surfactant molecules form a dispersed phase; below TK hydrated crystals are formed (Figure 8A). In the figure 8B, surface tension versus log of the bulk phase concentration for an aqueous solution of a surfactant is represented. Three distinctive parts of the curve represent: I. At low surfactant concentrations surfactant monomers are forming monolayer at the air/water interface. II. At concentrations below, but close to CMC slope of the curve is constant because surface concentration reached its

²⁵ Verma and Ghosh. *J SurfactantS Deterg.* 14(3):347-352 (2011).

²⁶ Jurašin and Sikirić. *Oligomerization of Chemical and Biological Compounds*, 133 (2014).

maximum value. III. At concentrations above cmc, surface tension remains almost constant, due to constant monomer concentration.

Using thermodynamic data and other experimental data, widely applicable and acceptable quantitative structure-activity(property) relationships (QSA(P)Rs) models have been established between basic structures and physicochemical properties. Those models are essential tools to guide the synthesis of desired formulations in different industrial sectors²⁷.

4.2. SECRETed QSA(P)R Approach.

The steps in a general procedure of QSA(P)R model construction using molecular descriptors are outlined below.

1. Split the dataset into training and test datasets for evaluating the predicted performance of the model.
2. Calculate numerous molecular descriptors of each compound in the datasets.
3. Construct a reliable model of the training dataset to predict the target activity or property from these calculated descriptors using classification or regression methods (e.g., multiple regression analysis, partial least squares regression, support vector machine (SVM), and random forest).
4. Evaluate the performance of the constructed model by predicting the target activities of the compounds in the test dataset that are not used for model construction.

SECRETed biosurfactant QSA(P)R study was developed from a biosurfactants database of 1300 compounds with known chemical structures. After the data collection, three different properties characterizing the surfactant capacity were analyzed: i) critical micellar concentration (CMC), ii) Krafft point and iii) surface tension. Because no experimental data for these properties were available in the database, our goal was to infer the data for the remaining compounds thanks to QSA(P)R modelling techniques.

As outlined in the previous section, to obtain strong and reliable models, the database was grouped into different chemical families, based on the presence of certain functional groups (Table 2, Figure 8).

After the construction of 14 different QSAR models, based on multi-linear regression analysis, the value of the properties under study was predicted for a maximum of 988 molecules, as is the case of CMC (Table 3).

²⁷ Hu et al. Int J Mol Sci. 11(3): 1020–1047(2010).

Table 3: SECRETed biosurfactant QSA(P)R modelling general statistics.

Modeled Property	Start BS_data (n° cmp with observed data)	Final BS_data (n° cmp with calculated data)	Infered BS_data (n° cmp without previous data)	% of infered BS_data	Prediction accuracy (R ²)*
CMC	298	1286	988	77	0.879
Surface tension	20	572	552	97	0.945
Krafft point	130	169	39	23	0.848

* average R-squared models; BS: biosurfactant; cmp: compound.

When analyzing the data in Table 2, it can be noted that there are three aspects to consider when inferring the experimental property value for the biosurfactants:

- 1) the chemical variability of the compounds whose experimental value is known (for the properties under study).
- 2) the number of compounds of a certain chemical family whose experimental value is unknown.
- 3) the property value variability of biosurfactant used to train the model, determines the model applicability domain.

An example of the importance of these three conditions is exemplified with the modelling surface tension property. Starting experimental data available for training surface tension model was the smallest one (just 20 biosurfactant with reported surface tension retrieved), but as explained in condition 2), it has been possible to infer surface tension value for a high number of compounds with unknown data (as biosurfactants chemical families #1 and #5 are composed by a total of 378 and 109 compounds, respectively there are many surface tension experimental values to infer) (Table 3). Likewise, it should be considered that, to model surface tension value from chemical family #2 biosurfactants, synthetic surfactants were used to train the model; however, this algorithm (prior external validation) has been applied to the prediction of chemical family #2 biosurfactants surface tension (consisting of 90 compounds) (Table 2).

The opposite case is reflected by the percentage of compounds whose Krafft point value has been inferred from the QSA(P)R models (Table 3). In this specific case, experimental data was available for 130 biosurfactants; however, the experimental Krafft point was only calculated for 169 compounds. This fact is explained in point 1), as just Krafft point information was retrieved for biosurfactants belonging to chemical families (#5 and #8) and 3), since QSA(P)R models are subject to their range of applicability domain. Outside this applicability domain, QSA(P)R model should not be applied in order to maintain the expected predictive capability.

4.3. SECRETed CMC QSA(P)R models.

In Table 4, a summary of QSAR models developed to predict biosurfactants' CMC values from the database is reported.

The descriptors used in the construction of the CMC QSAR models belong fundamentally to these subcategories: autocorrelation, atom type e-state, aromatic atom and atom count, information content, molecular distance edge, sum of constitutional and topological charge descriptors.

Figure 10 shows the CMC calculated values (μM) distribution along SECRETed biosurfactant MFs, together with the highlight of the training data set, that is, biosurfactants with observed experimental values.

Table 4: Summary of QSAR models developed to predict biosurfactants CMC (μM) values.

Chemical family	N° Compound training set	Model prediction capacity (R^2)
1	50	0.839
2	42	0.831
3	7	0.983
4	33	0.862
5	28	0.814
6	36	0.870
7	24	0.904
8	12	0.930
9	8	0.824
	240* (Total)	0.873 (average)

*Note that the number of total compounds used for training the QSAR models does not coincide with the starting number of compounds allocated in the different chemical families, this is because part of these compounds has been used as external test set for model validation. The models whose starting data was very small have been subjected to an internal validation process.

Figure 10. SECRETed Biosurfactant MFs CMC values distribution (μM). A) Calculated and observed values. B) Training set of biosurfactants with observed CMC values (red nodes).

4.4. SECRETed Surface Tension QSA(P)R models.

In Table 5, a summary of QS(P)AR models developed to predict biosurfactants surface tension values from our database is reported.

Autocorrelation descriptors were used in the construction of the surface tension QSAR models.

Figure 11 shows the Surface Tension calculated values (mN/m) distribution along SECRETed biosurfactant MFs, together with the highlight of the training data set, that is, biosurfactants with observed experimental values.

Table 5: Summary of QSAR models developed to predict biosurfactants Surface Tension (mN/m) values

Chemical family	N° Compound training set	Model prediction capacity (R ²)
1	6	0.965
5	5	0.926
2*	10	0.944
	11** (Total)	0.945 (average)

* Completed with data from synthetic surfactants.

** sum of the biosurfactant compounds used in the QSAR models (only those belonging to chemical families #1 and #5).

Figure 11. SECRETed Biosurfactant MFs Surface Tension values distribution (mN/m). A) Calculated and observed values. B) Training set of biosurfactants with observed Surface Tension values (red nodes).

4.5. SECRETed Kraftt point QSA(P)R models.

In Table 6, a summary of QSA(P)R models developed to predict of biosurfactants Kraftt point values from our database is reported.

MOE and autocorrelation descriptors were used in the construction of the Krafft point QSAR models.

Figure 12 shows the Krafft point calculated values (°C) distribution along SECRETed biosurfactant MFs, together with the highlight of the training data set, that is, biosurfactants with observed experimental values.

Table 6: Summary of QSAR models developed to predict biosurfactants Krafft point (°C) values

Chemical family	N° Compound training set	Model prediction capacity (R ²)
5	12	0.872
8	92	0.824
	104 (Total)	0.848 (average)

Figure 12. SECRETed Biosurfactant MFs Krafft point distribution (°C). A) Calculated and observed values. B) Training set of biosurfactants with observed Krafft point values (red nodes).

5. SECRETed biochemical space decomposition.

The overarching goal of SECRETed is to unlock the potential of marine and extremophilic bacteria as a source of tailor-made amphiphilic molecules by means of i) an extended bioactivity screening in 4 different aquatic microbial collections ii) sequenced based screening of novel marine and extremophilic genomes and metagenomes and iii) the formulation and validation of a ‘mix and match’ approach where modular genetic elements will be combined to get new tailor-made compounds based on their amphipathic nature.

However, although the chemical structures of a large number of SECRETed compounds are known (around 1900 molecular structures), the metabolic pathways that lead to their synthesis are not yet known (no more than 130 compounds with defined biosynthetic routes).

Currently, the identification of relevant enzymes in a putative pathway is carried out by trial and error based on knowledge and experience; therefore, an information science-based approach is highly desirable.

A large variety of natural products are produced from a limited variety of starting materials²⁸. So, as a starting point to guide retrosynthesis efforts, we addressed the molecular decomposition of SECRETed biochemical space into their metabolic intermediates.

There are multiple advantages to this approach:

First, this approach determines the possible R-group decompositions of a given target molecule. The query molecule consists of the scaffold and ligand attachment points represented by R-groups. The query molecule can be input as SMARTS, or it can be searched through the implementation of tools such as the Maximum Common Substructure (MCSS)²⁹. The advantage of R-group decomposition is that it can be complemented with biological information, which makes it possible to identify structural changes that modify biological activity or other properties.

Second, It also helps into the elucidation of biosynthetic pathways, since the identification of common metabolic intermediates points into common reactions (specially when related to the same MFs). Specially when MFs can also be structurally related molecules based on their mass spectral fragmentation patterns, whereas Gene cluster families are biosynthetic gene clusters that show similar gene cluster organization with a high degree of sequence similarity³⁰.

Finally, the definition of the basic building blocks that composes complex molecular structures potins to the selection of common metabolic precursors. Classifying biosurfactants and

²⁸ Dewick . Medicinal natural products: a biosynthetic approach 3rd ed. Chichester, England: John Wiley & Sons; (2009)

²⁹ Y. Cao et al., Bioinformatics, 24 pp. i366-i374 (2008),

³⁰ Nguyen et al., Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 110(28):E2611-20. (2013).

siderophores from this perspective helps the selection of proper microbial host based on their ability to produce massived precursors under industrial production conditions.

For this purpose, we employed the Metabolic disassembler tool³¹. However, several improvements had to be implemented since the original code of metabolic disassembler was able to disassemble 344 out of 1912, a 17,99%.

This required improving the original code to reduce execution times and memory usage, to favour the computation of large datasets (as in our case, more than 1000 examples), and expand the original reference dataset.

In this way, we could successfully disassemble an overall 86.3 % of a total of 1912 molecules. Figure 13 provides a graphical display of one example of molecule modular disassembling and summarises KEGG ontology terms that represent major building blocks in SECRETed biochemical space.

Figure 13. A) Example of molecule modular disassembling. B) SECRETed biochemical space building blocks according KEGG ontology.

³¹Amano et al., BMC Bioinformatics 20(1):728.(2019)

6. Conclusions.

Central to SECRETed main objectives is to construct a unique microbial amphiphilic compound space comprehending molecular structures, physicochemical characteristics, associated bioactivities, and revealed genetic mechanisms responsible for their biosynthesis.

Moreover, it draws the baseline for the advances that are envisioned in SECRETed workflow.

The obtention of SECRETed conciliated molecular information has emphasised the need for this meta-analysis. The need for integrative analytical biosurfactants and siderophores databases has also been addressed in the past^{32,33}. However, there is still the need of connecting such databases to their potential functionalities and their ability to be applied at an industrial scale.

By clustering chemical structures in Molecular Networks (MNs), molecular similarities and associated features will pave the way to elucidate QSAR/QSPR models aiming to infer structure-properties links. The development of these MNs will also help in molecular dereplication when structural information will be collected.

MNs can combine the layering of multi-informational data, such as taxonomical and biological data, to reinterpret SECRETed biochemical space from a different perspective. For example, establishing which genetic clusters and subclusters are responsible for the biosynthesis of the target molecules will also guide SECRETed microbial sequencing efforts facilitating a genetic dereplication platform.

Not only that, MNs can help in the elucidation of Molecular families (MFs) and their connection to gene clusters families (GCFs). This ultimately helps classify enzyme families and their substrate specificities, essential information for SECRETed retrosynthesis algorithms.

In summary, this public report has summarised SECRETed efforts into the obtention and conciliation of biosurfactants and siderophore databases.

³² Jorge et al., Database 1-8 (2015)

³³ Garber et al., Front Microbiol. 11: 37 (2020).